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GEOTECHNICAL ASPECTS OF THE RECONSTRUCTION OF THE BALLINAMORE AND BALLYCONNELL CANAL

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1969

Presentation to Geotechnical Society of the Institution on 8th February 1994

SYNOPSIS

The Drumlin terrain of Leitrim, Cavan and Fermanagh whilst presenting the passerby with picturesque visits and beautiful memories also provides the river and canal engineer with experiences of a unique nature.

Geotechnical aspects of the reconstruction of raised canal, canalised river with 16 locks, 34 bridges and associated facilities are presented here.

INTRODUCTION

The Ballinamore and Ballyconnell Canal was built in the middle of the 19th century to provide a commercial waterway link between the river systems of the Shannon and the Erne.

Abandoned in 1869, after only 9 years of service, it has been completely reconstructed 120 years later as a navigable water system for modern pleasure cruisers. The link creates a 750km continuous navigable inland waterway system for recreation which is unique in Europe.

The reconstruction was managed, designed and constructed by ESB International over a planned three year period and will be maintained and operated by the Office of Public Works in Ireland and the Department of Agriculture in Northern Ireland

Site investigation was divided into three basic phases, first a series of:

- Preliminary Investigations to provide a basis for the scheme design, second a set of
- Detailed site specific investigations for individual construction contracts, and thirdly
- Ongoing investigations during construction.

Furthermore, it was decided to appoint a Specialist Soils Consultant to ESB International to review and advise where necessary. Professor Eamon Hanrahan had been involved with the Office of Public Works on this canal and therefore his services were retained.

The Original Scheme

The original scheme was built under the auspices of the Commissioners for Public Works by Messrs. William T. Mulvaney and John McMahon. Work began in 1846 and consisted of three sections.

- A rise of 8 locks over 10km from the Shannon at Leitrim Village to the summit at Lough Scur in Stillwater.
- A summit reach of 4.8km of level water from Lough Marave to Lough Scur.
- A fall of 8 locks over 45km from Lough Scur to the Upper Erne in the canalised Woodford river.

The project took 4 years to plan and 17 years to complete and included 34 bridges

and accommodated the conflicting interest of drainage and navigation. Due to difficulties beyond the control of the constructors, such as finance and the advance of the railways the canal had a useful life of 9 years, less than it took to build. It was abandoned and the link closed by nature reverted to a free river and clogged man made canal.

Geology and Channel Morphology

The predominant geological features of this watershed canal are Drumlin terrain interspersed with extensive post-glacial alluvial flats divided at the summit by a significant limestone rock outcrop. The alluvial flats comprise silts, clays, organic mixtures and deposits of sand and gravel and these materials occur on their own or in layered formation.

The abandoned canal, its engineering works combined with the unchecked flow, allowed the Woodford river to continue its natural meandering regime which is typical of rivers in the alluvial reaches adjacent to upland areas. The continuous process of lateral channel movement with bed degradation was evident throughout the canal. The sedimentation of bed load was most obvious at the entrances to lakes, where with the sudden drop in velocity the river deposited its burden.

The man-made stillwater section meanwhile was overgrown, dewatered and blocked with bank slips and silt deposits which reduced it to a deep drain in some areas.

PRELIMINARY DESIGN AND SITE INVESTIGATIONS

Preliminary Design

The reconstruction work was defined in 1989/90 in a series of feasibility, implementation, cost and environmental reports which were independently audited and approved by the EC.

The shear size and spread of the site, 62.5km long with an area of the order of 1.1 million square metres excluding the 14 lakes and their perimeters called for preliminary design and site investigations to be carried out simultaneously.

The main construction features of the scheme were identified in ESB International's Implementation Plan as:

- Constructing embankments, with by-pass channels on the section from the Shannon to the summit at Lough Scur.
- Deepening and widening sections of the

Woodford River channel between Lough Scur and the Erne

- To minimise impact and to stay clear of environmentally sensitive areas carrying out the work from one bank only or using floating plant.
- Major lake dredging.
- Replacing, underpinning or repairing 34 bridges.
- Demolishing, constructing and refurbishing 16 locks and weirs.
- Providing several public mooring areas with modern facilities.

The project being divided into a series of contracts required the geotechnical investigations to be programmed to suit.¹

Structures such as bridges, locks, weirs, moorings and small ancillary buildings which are site specific, can be easily catered for with standard site investigation techniques.

River Engineering works over a 62.5km length, however, require a somewhat different approach due to the rapid changes in ground conditions which can occur over short distances.

Major cost elements of this project were the excavation and embankment construction in very soft alluvial soils and dredging in lakes. In addition the prevention of water loss in dry seasons was a key element of the functioning of the completed canal.

Preliminary Site Investigations & Trials

Five priorities were identified in association with the sequence of contracts to be let

- The composition of the banks of the canal.
- The embankments to be constructed on the soft silts and organic deposits in the area known locally as the Black Lake, from Leitrim to Lock 15.
- The channel cross section would be a corner stone of the entire project (because it determines quantities of excavation and fill and from that the amount of land required to accommodate the side slopes, spoil deposit and maintenance access).

As a follow on to this the slope at which the silty organic lake bed material could maintain its profile after dredging.

- The water lost in suspect areas of rock and bypassing the locks which were to be refurbished.
- The location and extent of rock to be excavated.

Having identified the key design factors and the priorities it was decided to embark on a number of full scale site trials in association with standard site investigation works.

Very early on in the project the aim and method of construction was guided by environmental considerations. Selection of engineering solutions was an iterative process which considered such diverse topics as vegetation growth, boat activity, soil strengths, visual inputs and economic considerations to mention but a few.

The aim was to provide a canal which employed the least amount of artificial bank stability and relied more on the natural ability of the soils and vegetation whilst the method had to minimise the impact and maximise the recovery.

Bank Composition

A detailed look at the sight commenced immediately in parallel with background studies.

Swedish Auger

With 54km of canal bank, most of its inaccessible to mobile plant, a portable hand operated system is the only economic option. ESB International have extensive experience of soil classification, on other projects covering larger areas, using the Swedish Auger and chose to use this for the canal.

The equipment consists of a 1.0m long 50mm diameter steel auger section which is hand turned. Extension rods are screw fitted as penetration increases to a maximum depth of 7.5m from ground level. This depth can be increased by the addition of extra rods, but is limited by the power of the operator, particularly in stiffer soils. The 7.5m depth coincides with the depth of main significance in regard to bed and bank stability. The auger is extracted by means of a hand-operated lightweight hydraulic jack. The entire system is highly portable.

200 boreholes were augured and logged at intervals of up to 250m along the canal. Logging included chainages, type of material at the various strata and depth to refusal. In addition samples were taken for laboratory testing of moisture content at 31

locations where it was expected to encounter very soft material.

An examination of the moisture contents of these samples revealed a wide variation from soft clay at 30% through stiff clay at 122% to soft peat at 440%.

These investigations provided a wealth of information on the soils to be encountered and helped in the determination of design profiles, excavation and spoil deposition parameters as well as identifying areas where further more extensive investigations would be required.

High moisture contents for example meant that rehabilitation of spoil heaps would consider the volume changes and run off difficulties associated with drying out.

As well as identifying soft areas possible rock sites were found which were not encountered in the background studies.

Wagon Drill

Of equal importance to soft materials is the occurrence of large quantities of rock to be excavated or built upon and these were identified at bridge, lock and channel sites. In order to prove rock at the 32 identified sites a mobile system was necessary. The sites were limited in number and, therefore, access was not a difficulty.

Again ESB International drew on its experience in this field with a tractor mounted rock drilling rig in proving rock depths.

Detailed boring logs were recorded, setting out the results of the rock drills.

Analysis and comparison of the results with other investigations showed that descriptions such as cavities were more likely to

be continuous solution hollows. It was noted that there were some differences between this and other conventional investigations detailed further on in this paper. In particular thickness of shattered rock varied, however, the exact locations of the two investigations also varied.

FULL SCALE SITE TRIALS

Trial No. 1 - Embankments on Stillwater Canal- See Plate 1

The site chosen for Trial No. 1 was in the Leitrim Townland of Tiermactiernan, at a chainage of 1450 metres, between the two lowest locks on the system.

Site selection was made to meet the requirement of a representative exercise taking account of the many restrictions on site access in the early days.

Initial probe surveys showed that the existing embankments were constructed using the in-situ bed materials. The materials in the embankment consisted of random mixtures of silt, silty-clay and peat as would be expected from cut-fill by hand.

It was planned to test if this material could be used to form new embankments to bring the canal up to modern standards of water depth and surface widths. In theory this would be difficult, however, in practise the banks were there and basically sound after 120 years.

The trial consisted of isolating a 30m stretch with temporary weirs across the canal to divert water away from the works into cleaned up back drains. Forming embankments in-situ and filling with water and monitoring the performance over a 3-week period.

PLATE 1

As work commenced on site in September 1989 the weather took a turn for the worse with daily heavy rainfall. The material proved impossible to work with in these wet conditions. Moisture contents were ranging up to 123% at various depths and were too wet to be remoulded.

This would be of grave concern in full contracts and for stability of completed embankments. What was almost a dry drain now became a fast flowing torrent due to the clear passage from the summit at Lough Scur.

The trial was re-directed to investigate the use of imported fill placed on the existing embankments to form the new profile. Topsoil was stripped for re-use and surplus soft excavation disposed off site.

Suitable import material had to be found, locally to be economical. A dis-used rock quarry was selected where the overburden was available in sufficient quantities for the reconstruction work as well as the trial. The material was a gravel-sand-silt clay mixture. The grading curves together with the moisture content (19%), density ($1.6t/m^3$) and Atterberg limits (LL 40.7, PL 21.5, PI 19.2) indicated a satisfactory fill material.

Settlement during placing and compacting was expected to occur. However, the settlement was excessive and eventually about double the nominal quantity of imported material was required. Considerable difficulties were encountered in getting the material on site with a continuous repair to temporary access routes across very soft soil, dump trucks getting stuck and churning up the already placed materials. At this stage the amount of water in the canal from the rainfall was adequate for trials and therefore the cut off weirs were not required to retain water.

Monitoring consisted of level measurements and visual inspection of the toes and slopes to check erosion and leakage.

After the severe construction settlement there were only minor changes in level and there was no erosion or leakage at 6 months. As a result of the construction difficulties it was decided to lower the bed rather than raise the banks. This was done by cutting the canal into the hill, about which it was skirting, for about 1km. This results in no embankments on the right bank and minor alterations to the left bank which was for the most part satisfactory. The costs associated with lowering the

PLATE 2

canal bed were more economical than importing material to form embankments.'

Trial No. 2 - Lock Water Loss on Stillwater Canal-See Plate 2

The purpose of this trial was to determine if water could bypass the existing locks, which were to be refurbished, through the existing backfill material.

The chosen site was Lock 15 in the same general area as Trial No. 1 and carried out under the same contract.

The procedure was to install dam beams in the upper level of the lock, form an embankment upstream of this and fill with water the enclosed section of canal.

It was discovered here, as at almost every other structure location that the lock was constructed on good ground and immediately upstream we were in a quagmire. The continuous rain made progress very slow and the excavation work difficult. The soil encountered was a blue clay which was completely impermeable. It could not be worked when wet and would not drain. When walking on this material a man would sink up to his hips and would have great difficulty in escaping. One advantage of the material was its use in

providing a seal on the dam beam/lock masonry interface.

When the trial section was filled with water up to the design level and monitored there was no significant water loss after a 24 hour dry period.

Trial No. 3 - Water Loss at Lough Scur-see Plate 3

The significant rock outcrop between the Stillwater section and the summit at Lough Scur was a potential water loss area and was 7-8 km from Leitrim Village.

PLATE 3

A trial was conducted by sealing off both ends of this cutting with two temporary weirs approximately 1.0km apart. The weirs were constructed using reno mattresses and gabions. Water tightness was achieved by polythene lining and cement grouting the weir/rock interface. The rock surface was cleaned and prepared with blinding concrete prior to placing the weirs. An expanded polystyrene blanket was placed between the gabions and the polythene lining to prevent puncturing.

The section between the weirs was filled by pumping from Lough Scur to design level. Monitoring of water levels in the trial were over a week long period before the gabions were completely removed. No significant water loss was measured and after heavy rain showers a gain was noted.

In association with the trial 3 no. boreholes were drilled in the banks of the rock cut to investigate permeability and rock fracturing by means of standard packer tests and core recovery. Boreholes were sunk to around 12m below ground level which is approximately 5m below channel bed level. The material encountered was grey limestone rock. Packer tests were carried out at and below channel level. At channel level permeability proved to be negligible and below it was zero. Core recovery gave RQD and SCR values in the high 50's, 80's and 90's. The boreholes and packer tests confirmed a thin covering of peat, marl and

clay overlying a compact mass of limestone.

The packer tests, at substantial pressure of 206 kPa (30 psi), with the trial results showed that this was not an area of concern for water loss.

Trial No. 4 - Cutting on Woodford River-see Plate 4

The site chosen for this trial was an area close to St. John's Lough. This stretch of river over a 2km length was reported to exhibit channel upheaval and caused considerable problems in the original scheme. In particular around chainage 14000 all the problems associated with cuttings in Drumlin terrain were present. High ground on both sides, poor drainage, seepage and mixed layers of gravel and peat. There were other areas along the river with similar problems and this location was chosen to carry out a trial on the most severe cutting to be encountered in the project.

Eight boreholes were sunk in a line across the canal. The boreholes showed soft or very soft organic silt or peaty clay in depths of 18-25m and water under pressure gushed up the boreholes when rock was reached. Soil samples were recovered for laboratory testing and in-situ strength tests were carried out using SPT, Shear Vane and Dutch cone penetrometer.

Analysis of potential slip circles and failure modes with measured shear strengths as low as 5 KPa showed that these soils were unsuitable for supporting any significant overburden.

Analysis showed the factor of safety against rotational slip to be close to 1.0 and possibly less. Creep tests were carried out and confirmed the vulnerability of this organic silt to continuing strain by creep. The nett effect of this was that design values of shear strength obtained from penetrometer, triaxial and shear vane testing were reduced by 50% to allow for reduced strength due to creep and increased strain.

The conclusion was that the best solution to the instability was to provide gentle side

slopes, thereby reducing overburden pressure and removing spoil beyond the zone of influence of the canal, i.e. 1.5 times the canal width from the edge.

The trial section was excavated using these design parameters. As forecast the excavation revealed a mixture of silts, gravels and peats. Ground water level, ground level and erosion were monitored and after 6 months no movements had occurred. Canal water levels had risen and fallen during the period and there was local erosion of the toe where the excavation had removed a tree stump. No significant rising of the bed had occurred and minor differences in levels were attributed to the difficulty of excavating 'blind' below water level. The conclusions were that gentle slopes with underwater excavation would be satisfactory. No doubt had this option been available to the original scheme they would have saved considerable expense, and time whilst solving insurmountable difficulties.

Trial No. 5 - Lake Dredging

The final trial was to determine the stability in-situ and the handling characteristics of the dredged materials.

The Woodford river and its tributaries are relatively young and are undergoing a continuous change in morphology in terms of bed degradation. A comparison of OS maps of the area back to 1836 confirms this. In several locations large tributaries were diverted into the lakes in the original scheme so as to minimise the bed load of the canal. Recovery of samples from all of the lakes to be dredged confirmed that the material was almost identical at each location and consisted of an organic silt which was very prone to disintegrate and liquify almost instantaneously.

Ballymagauran Lough was chosen for a trial, again for reasons of site access and suitability. Hydrographic Surveys were carried out before and after the trial. Excavation was to be by water borne plant and the spoil, with high water content, was to be contained within a bunded adjacent land area with a baffle weir.

Dredging is a specialised operation and therefore the methods were the responsibility of the contractor. Basic data was provided on the material for their information. The contractor opted for suction with an agitator and delivery to the spoil heap by floating pipe. This proved unsuccessful despite many attempts and finally a floating hydraulic excavator approach was adopted. This proved to be acceptable and was the method adopted for the dredging contracts. Spoil was removed by floating barge to spoil heaps.

PLATE 4

Monitoring of the trial dredging consisted of hydrographic level and alignment surveys to determine if slips or upheaval occurred. The result was that a side slope of 1:20 with a 20 metre channel width was selected as the design slope.

DETAILED SITE INVESTIGATION

There are 34 bridges, 16 locks, 12 weirs, 33 mooring sites including 6 fully serviced public moorings. Of these 10 bridges were replaced, 8 locks replaced and all moorings installed. Detailed site investigations were carried out at each location. These consisted of combinations of auger probing, rock proving, trial pits, boreholes and dutch cones on land and geophysical radar in the lakes.

Probing and rock proving have already been detailed. Trial pits were of the standard type, hydraulic excavation with logging of materials, water levels and strata.

Boreholes-See Plate 5

A total of 50 boreholes were put down to varying depths at specified locations. The bulk of these boreholes were for construction of locks, bridges, weirs and moorings.

The method used was the standard cable percussion, otherwise known as the shell and auger.

200mm diameter steel tubes were used and stiff clays and obstructions were broken up by chiselling. Disturbed and undisturbed samples were taken for laboratory testing. Tests included Atterberg limits, organic matter content, specific gravity, shear strength, grading curves, moisture contents, tri-axials, density, consolidation and creep. In-situ testing consisted of piezometer, SPT, shear vane, packer and core recovery.

All boreholes and testing were in accordance with British Standard Code of Practice for Site Investigation, B.S. 5930.

Dutch Cone- See Plate 6

The Dutch cone has been in use, especially in the Netherlands for almost a half-century. It is most suitable for the type of soils encountered on the Ballinamore Ballyconnell Canal. The apparatus used was a variation on the Dutch cone called a Piezocone, so called because it can measure porewater characteristics. The value of a piezocone is enhanced when a comparison vane shear programme is carried out. Consequently, a comparison programme was implemented at several locations including trials 1 and 4 to compare soil type at different locations.

Undrained shear strength was measured using a standard vane test or estimated from piezocone results.

The piezocone was driven into the ground by a portable electro-hydraulic system. Reactionary forces were countered by auger anchors. The results were continuously recorded as a plot against depth of end resistance, friction ratio, porewater pressure and dissipation. The results were then analysed. Friction ratio and end resistance were used for soil classification whilst effective shear stress was determined using end resistance and pore pressure. Dissipation of pore water was used to estimate co-efficients of consolidation. Pore water readings were used to indicate pore water pressure.

PLATE 5

Care is necessary in the interpretation of results from both the shear vane and piezocone. The vane is subject to correction factors of up to 50% due to size and rate effects. The piezocone requires a number of cross checks to arrive at a true shear strength and end cone resistances were reduced by a factor of 25. The pore water pressure is artificially high during driving. Whilst these readings were satisfactory for the various calculations of strengths the true porewater pressure is obtained by stopping the probe in-situ and allowing the excess porewater pressure to dissipate. A period of more than 24 hours is required for this.

The main advantage of this investigation was the speed at which the results were obtained and the highly portable nature of the apparatus.

Geophysical Radar Survey

Channel excavation in the stretch from Loughs Erne to Garadice was, for environmental and land acquisition reasons to be carried out from floating plant within the banks and shores of the lakes.

The geophysical radar survey method was given a trial to assess its compatibilities for estimating both soft rock material. The method was found to be successful and adopted for the full stretch.

The equipment was compact and mobile and used transducers to send electromagnetic pulses to the lake bed from where it was reflected back. The results were continuously recorded as a trace as the boat

PLATE 6

CONSTRUCTION

Work commenced on site with the small "Lough Scur" contract in February 1991. This contract consisted of some weir and bridge repairs at Boneil, the mooring at Keshcarrigan and varied channel and lake excavation. It was intended that lessons learned on this contract would be used in overcoming the problems indicated in the site investigation and in deciding the work packages and detailed programme for the remainder of the work. It was quickly confirmed that:

- Transport of any quantity of spoil material along small public roads would quickly lead to their structural failure.
- Likewise transport of spoil along even raised stony banks would be virtually impossible in the six wettest winter months.
- Silt traps in the channel were unlikely to be effective in limiting transport of suspended material.
- Masonry in bridges and locks was bound with a very strong cementitious material, which was lost when exposed to quick flowing water.
- During dry summer months with canal water low, lightweight excavators on mats could excavate in the poorest ground conditions at a fraction of dredging cost.
- Soil conditions were likely to vary considerably. For example in one 100m section rock, boulder clay, 100% peat and clayey silt with peat were encountered.
- The original canal engineers operating 150 years ago had a remarkable ability to find every occurrence of hard ground near the surface and to use it to advantage.

In the Lock Scur area for instance weir 8 was founded on flat rock at bed level while lock 8 was a little downstream where the

rock suddenly fell away. An isolated rock outcrop was found for scuw bridge and flat rock at bed level was used for the landing stage at Keshcarrigan.

PROGRAMME

Given the target to open the canal for commercial operation in the spring of 1994, it was clear in the spring of 1991,

- that the summers of 1991 and 1992 should be used to complete the weather sensitive work.
- the summer of 1993 should then be available for completion of difficult areas, trials and fine tuning.
- most of the banks should have revegetated naturally before exposure to heavy traffic.

This outline programme has in fact been achieved and indeed a navigation stabilisation contract will be complete before the canal is opened in April 1994.

SPOIL DEPOSITION AREAS

Temporary acquisition of land required for construction areas and spreading of spoil was negotiated prior to entry. Given that during the first two summers work progressed in about fifty areas at any one time and that well over 500 landowners and occupiers were dealt with, land acquisition was a major concern of all those involved in managing the project.

Where spoil was to be deposited beside the canal, bank stability was one factor which determined the amount of land required. For example in the canal between Drumany and Muckcross bridges, where spoil was deposited on the banks, part of the canal was excavated at a slope of 1:1.5 and part at 1:3. Plate 7 illustrates that at 1:1.5 the temporarily acquired 65m wide strip is required to accommodate 34m³ of excavation per metre run. However, in less stable ground, assuming no material is

deposited within 1.5 times the width of the canal, a 125m strip is required for 65m³ per metre run.

In other canal sections and at lakes major deposition areas were acquired at intervals. Stable deposition areas were particularly valuable in parts of the canal with weak banks and low excavation quantities.

Settlement tests revealed that lake material if mixed with water in the ratio 5 to 1 would take about 4 months to return to its original moisture content. Cutter suction dredging was, therefore, ruled out and every effort was made to avoid increasing the moisture content of the spoil. Generally spoil deposited on banks was grassed in the same or the following summer. Lake sediment deposited in bunds greater than 1.0m deep appears to require about 2 to 4 years settlement before full restoration is possible.

BANK STABILITY

The stability of banks was a major concern along much of the canals length. To illustrate this some of the more interesting areas are examined.

The Black Lake

The site investigation described the soil in this area as a soft to very soft blue/grey clay under either a stiff grey silty clay or peat. Plate 8 gives typical before and after cross sections. To achieve the design cross section the following difficulties arose:

- Although excavation was done after the canal had been dry for some months, the northern banks on which machines travelled tended to slump inwards and some bed upheaval was also evident.
- The southern undisturbed embankment tended to crack at the top of the bank and to form a small slip circle.

PLATE 7

It became apparent that reducing the northern bank slope to 1:3 and pushing back the spoil from the bank did not stabilise it. Native timber piles 8.0m long were then tried. They were driven in using the excavator bucket in lines at 2.0m centres. Up to 4 lines of piles were generally required to achieve stability. This technique was also repeated on the southern embankment where necessary. It had the advantage of being relatively economical and vibration free and utilised the only equipment that could gain access.

In the following six months the southern embankment was seen to have settled. Up to 500mm of material 3.0m wide was placed on the crest of the embankment and this has held to date.

It can be seen, therefore, that the choice of design bed level was critical as either a higher embankment or a lower northern bank would have been very expensive. The canal level in this area was in fact reduced by 1.2m compared with the original and this involved underpinning at two locks.

It is interesting to note that a factor of safety of 1.5 against bank failure with water in the canal equates approximately to a factor of safety between 1.0 and 1.12 for a dry canal.

This provides a degree of comfort where for practical reasons excavation was done in the dry. However, sudden drawdown of the canal should be avoided in critical areas.

Bank Movements during Construction

The vast majority of bank failures which occurred during construction involved only the soil within a few metres of the top and bottom of one bank. Only on a few occasions was bottom upheaval observed. Although cracking frequently appeared near the top of the slope it was rare to observe an intact wedge of bank which would be associated with a single slip circle after the failure.

The failure mechanism appeared to involve more slumping movement than slip circle movement, which is not surprising given the generally high moisture content. Occasionally these failures were associated with a weak zone overlying a gravel layer or rock surface occurring around bed level.

Three large bank failures occurred at Aghalane, Lisnatulla and Dunmany which virtually blocked the channel. In each

instance many surface crack lines were apparent after the movement for a distance of 20 to 30 metres back from the bank. The bank material slumped down a depth of approximately 1.0m and the lengths of the failures varied from 60 to 140m. Again more slumping movement than a slip circle was apparent. It is interesting to note that all failures occurred at the junction of a stiff boulder clay deposit and the more usual peaty silty clayey deposit. Many of the smaller slips also occurred adjacent to a deposit of boulder clay or rock.

Stabilisation of these failures generally required time for the soil to dry out and gain more shear strength, together with up to four rows of timber piles near the channel banks. Although the vast majority of failures occurred after the canal was excavated, in no instance was an excavator involved in the movement. Failures usually occurred days or weeks after excavation.

Bank Based Excavation

Following lessons learned in the earlier part of the job the following modus operandi proved successful in difficult sections of the work:

- maintain good drainage on the worked bank
- strip topsoil, excavate and remove spoil from bank in one continuous operation
- where appropriate reduce bank height near the channel.
- reduce bank slopes where necessary (flatest used 1:5).
- a pre-emptive line of piles may prevent bank failure.
- watch out for ground adjacent to good ground which is often weaker than expected.

PLATE 8 TYPICAL BLACK LAKE SECTION

PLATE 9 ROCK ARMOUR ON SOUTH BANK D/S LOCK 2

Bank Erosion

A considerable portion of the canal between Skelan and Cloncoohey runs through weakly bound stony deposits which were concealed from view on the banks by a lining of clays and silts containing organic material. On deepening and widening the canal, the organic material was removed and bank erosion took place in a number of locations. Although a few metres of bank was lost in places, no action was taken other than to remove some stony material from the bed.

These banks now appear to have stabilised themselves in most locations. However, there were a number of stretches particularly where the banks were high that were subject to considerable erosion in winter. Rock armour as indicated in figure 12 is being used in these areas. An additional reason for this rock armour is to prevent bank collapse which has occurred in this stretch of canal.

Surprisingly erosion is not a major problem elsewhere in the canal, even where lenses of gravel were encountered. Some minor siltation has occurred at the intersection of bed and bank in places. In the poorest of organic silty clays some "oozing" of bank material through the lines of timber piles was noted, but this also seems to have stabilised.

A determined effort was made in the initial stages of the work to retain as many trees as possible. However, it was found that where a tree was close to the bank, rapid erosion took place around the roots of the trees and they were eventually removed. This was particularly noticeable in the stony areas described above, but occurred in all soil types.

The best vegetation for bank stabilisation would, therefore, appear to be naturally occurring rushes, reeds, grasses, etc. Grass seed was used in many areas to initiate vegetation of banks.

LEAKAGE

A water shortage is anticipated at Lough Scur, the canal summit, once every two or three years during drought periods. In addition it was known that the original canal engineers had found leakages into limestone fissures in this stretch at Kilclare. Although puddle clay protected by cut stone was still evident, it was thought that considerable leakage still existed.

Tests were carried out by sectioning off the canal using earthen bunds with a polythene lining. The limestone rock which occurred along much of this stretch was also examined after excavation.

In all it was necessary to seal 350m of canal. This was done using a 2mm polyethphene sheet on the bed protected by 100mm of concrete. Reinforced concrete side walls, sloped in soft ground were also used.

Cut off grout curtains were used to seal the ground adjacent to all locks. In addition the chamber walls at locks 9 to 16 where the old masonry was repaired were grouted. The grouting sealed most of the leakage and improved the structural strength of the locks.

Locks 4 and 5 were located on gravel beds which extended to a depth of 8 to 13m below the adjacent weirs. In all a total of 260 tonnes of cement were used to provide a grout curtain underneath and to the side of these weirs. 5% bentonite was also used to limit the grout lake and the w/c ratio was varied between 1 to 1 and 1 to .75.

Subsequent observations during summer drought periods confirmed that the canal sealing at Lock Scur and under the weirs was successful.

SUMMARY

In all a total of 700,000m³ of soft material and 104,440m³ of hard material were excavated. In addition 11,000 timber piles and 11,150m³ of rock armour were used to support the banks.

Looking to the future the reference books would suggest that a canalised river such as this requires four to five years to settle down. I believe that bank stability has been considerably improved over the last few years and that all the weakest areas have been dealt with. Some siltation will probably arise upstream of some of the weirs, but quantities will be small.

Ease of maintenance was one of the objectives in constructing this canal and there is every reason to believe that this has been achieved.

Acknowledgements

Authors wish to acknowledge with thanks the contributions to this project from all contractors and consultants. In particular we are grateful to our colleagues in ESB International, Professor Hanrahan, Kirk Mc Clure and Morton, the Office of Public Works and the Department of Agriculture.

Discussion

1. B. Quinn - timber piles, learned as they went along 2m spacing.
piles in 1m rows
2. R. Galbraith - corrections on vane shear strengths. up to 50%.
 $c_u = 5 \text{ kPa}$ from shear van \gg
 $q_c = 50 \text{ kPa}$ from piezocone \dots
3. - costs was £286 k. in 150 yrs ago. Present cost £30m.
Link to sea
i) via Lough Neagh is possible but very expensive
ii) Link via Limerick OK except bridges
iii) Link via B'shannon not poss
4. Pif Kauraha doubtful about use of piles. K'creed use for construction only.
↳ must have hard layer
to provide longitudinal stab.
did not deal with what was wrong bank too high
shear strength too low.
Why not use stone fill to stabilise toe.